

MODELLING DIABETES RISK FACTORS IN WOMEN: INSIGHTS FROM LOGISTIC REGRESSION AND PCA ON THE PIMA INDIAN DATASET

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ABSTRACT: *This study predicts the prevalence of diabetes among females and the associated risk factors with diabetes. The PIMA Indian data set available on the site of the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive Kidney Diseases (NIDDK) has been used for the prediction of diabetes status and the associated risks with it. To predict the vital clinical and physiological indicators like blood sugar level, Body Mass Index (BMI), pregnancy, and diabetes pedigree function Logistic regression has been implemented. The model was fitted well with the data. The prediction accuracy was found 78.26% with moderate sensitivity at 58.21% and high specificity at 89%. To find the significant features responsible for the diabetes risk and to reduce the dimensionality of the data we have utilized the Principal component analysis (PCA). After the dimension reduction overall accuracy reached 82.47%. The findings recommend the use of PCA to get the vital feature in the data to predict the diabetic condition that improves that model's accuracy.*

Key words: *Diabetes Prediction, Logistic Regression, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Diabetes Risk Factors*

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus, one of the most prevalent and rapidly expanding chronic diseases worldwide, has major public health implications. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), which accounts for the majority of cases among its different types, is characterized by insulin resistance and poor glucose metabolism. Women are especially susceptible to a distinct set of risk factors that significantly increase the likelihood of acquiring type 2 diabetes later in life because of their reproductive history, hormonal swings, and conditions like gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM).

According to several studies, women who have a history of GDM are much more likely to develop type 2 diabetes than women who do not [1–4]. This highlights the importance of early detection and monitoring of high-risk groups. Early intervention involving medication, lifestyle modifications, and routine screening can greatly delay or prevent diabetes. For risk stratification and preventive medicine, predictive modeling based on clinical, physiological, and demographic data is, therefore, a crucial tool. The Pima Indian Diabetes Dataset, made available by the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK), is one such extensive and extensively researched resource. This dataset, which contains biological and medical information from adult female patients with Pima Indian

Ancestry, has been widely used to develop and validate statistical and machine learning models for the prediction of diabetes.

To evaluate the role of different physiological and clinical characteristics—such as blood glucose, body mass index, number of pregnancies, and diabetes pedigree function—in predicting diabetes risk, we have utilized the logistic regression modelling in this study. To improve model efficiency and interpretability, we also include Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce the dimensionality of the factors to find the most important contributing factors for predicting diabetes. To predict the risk factors the dual strategy of using PCA and logistic regression provides deeper insights into the data's underlying structure. This modelling framework aims to enhance early diagnosis in female patients and provide guidance for clinical strategies. It is specifically designed for women who are at risk of developing diabetes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Prevalence and incidence of diabetes in women globally and regionally

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) prevalence was calculated by the International Association of Diabetes in Pregnancy Study Group (IADPSG) using data from 57 studies. The study found the regional variation in the incidence of diabetes, the combined global prevalence was 14.0%. WP and AFR had the second-highest standardised prevalence, after MENA and SEA. The three World Bank country income groups showed the highest standardised frequency in high-income nations. These standardised figures shed light on GDM's global picture [5].

A study estimated a 10.5% prevalence in 2021 among people aged 20 to 79 and a 12.2% prevalence in 2045 after analysing diabetes prevalence and health spending worldwide from 219 data sources between 2005 and 2020. Those between the ages of 75 and 79 had the highest incidence. Both urban areas and high-income nations have greater prevalence rates. According to the study, diabetes-related medical costs would reach \$1,054 billion USD worldwide by 2045, with middle-income nations seeing the most increase [6].

2.2 Impact of age, BMI, glucose levels, genetic predisposition, and reproductive history on diabetes risk.

A study was done to find the risk factors, both modifiable and non-modifiable, affected pregnant women's gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). It concentrated on age and mother preconception BMI, two important factors that influence insulin resistance. GDM was identified in 23.0% of the 3856 women. Advanced maternal age, gravidity, a history of spontaneous abortions during pregnancy, prior GDM, thyroid, and thrombophilic disorders were among the risk factors that could not be changed. The only risk factor that could be changed was preconception weight or obesity. Most diagnosis of GDM

were based on abnormalities in fasting glucose. In regions where GDM prevalence is high, interventions aimed at addressing maternal preconceptions about overweight and obesity may be successful in lowering GDM prevalence [7].

Women's function in reproduction causes them to undergo additional metabolic alterations. A study reviewed that how gender affects diabetes management, taking into account microbiome, hormone functions, body composition, glucose and fat metabolism, and gestational diabetes. Including gender in biomedical research enhances the scientific quality and applicability of knowledge while emphasising the differences' real-world applications [8].

2.3 Predictive Modelling in Diabetes Diagnosis

A study presented diabetes prediction algorithms and medicinal devices based on AI/ML. A number of AI/ML-based tools for patient self-management, clinical diagnosis support, and retinal screening have received approval from the US Food and Drug Administration. Nevertheless, traditional statistical risk stratification models outperform machine learning techniques in predicting new-onset diabetes [9].

A study divides patients into groups with and without diabetes using supervised machine learning techniques such SVM-linear, RBF kernel support vector machine, k-nearest neighbour, ANN, and multifactor dimensionality reduction [10].

Over 60 million individuals in Europe suffer from diabetes, a chronic metabolic disease that affects 415 million people globally. Because of poor diets, physical inactivity, and obesity, the prevalence is rising. An IoT-based system architecture that uses IPFS and block chain to forecast severe instances of diabetes is presented. On three datasets, the model's accuracy in classifying individuals with diabetes using an adaptive random forest approach was 85.9%, 99.5%, and 99.8% [11].

2.4 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in Biomedical Data

Use of the Pima Indian Diabetes Dataset in Research

A study suggested an e-diagnosis system for diabetes mellitus that uses machine learning techniques. The system makes use of J48 decision tree models, random forest classifiers, and Naïve Bayes classifiers. Analysis of each model's performance reveals that random forest performs better with more features and Naïve Bayes performs best with finer feature selection [12].

3. DATA AND METHDOLOGY

3.1 Data

For the of the diabetes condition in the patients we have used the Pima Indian data set provided by the national Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and the Kidney Diseases (NIDDK). The objective of the data set to diagnostically predict the presence of diabetes in female patients, in female patients, based

on a set of clinical and physiological measurements. The dataset is accessible through the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25421347.v1>.

3.2 Methodology

The present study uses the descriptive statistics to estimate difference in the health status of the diabetic and the non-diabetic females. To classify the factors responsible for the diabetic condition among the women this study used the Logistic regression. To improve the model accuracy and the predictability Principal component analysis used. PCA provides the significant factors responsible for the diabetes condition among the women, using these factors again logistic regression fitted.

3.3 Statistical Model for prediction of the Diabetes factors among the women

Let Y_i be the binary outcome of the i^{th} patient:

$$Y_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the patient has diabetes} \\ 0, & \text{if the patient does not have the diabetes} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Let X_i be the vector
 $= \{X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{ip}\}$ be the vector of the p predictor variables for the i^{th} patient

Where

$X_{i1} = \text{Age of the patient}$

$X_{i2} = \text{Pegnencies}$

$X_{i3} = \text{Glucose}$

$X_{i4} = \text{Blood Pressure}$

$X_{i5} = \text{Skin Thickness}$

$X_{i6} = \text{Insulin}$

$X_{i7} = \text{BMI}$

$X_{i8} = \text{DiabetesPedigreeFunction}$

The logistic regression model expressing the probability of the diabetes = $\pi_i =$

$$P(Y_i = 1|X_i) = \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{ip}}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{ip}}} \quad (2)$$

Or equivalently,

$$\text{Log} \frac{\pi_i}{(1 - \pi_i)} = \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{ip}}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{ip}}} \quad (3)$$

Where the π_i = represents that i^{th} patient actually have diabetes

β_0 = is equal to intercept

β_j = Regression coefficient

3.4 Parameter Estimation

The parameter of the models i.e. $\beta = (\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)$ are estimated by maximizing the likelihood function using the observed data $\{Y_i, X_i, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$

Or above equation can be written as log –likelihood function:

$$(\beta) = \sum Y_i \log(\pi_i) + (1 - Y_i) \log(1 - \pi_i) \quad (4)$$

The MLE $\hat{\beta}$ must satisfy the condition

$$\hat{\beta} = \text{arg}(\beta) \quad (5)$$

Numerical optimization methods are used to find the estimate of the $\hat{\beta}$

The Logistic regression results are presented in the Table-2

4. RESULT

4.1 Descriptive measures

The descriptive measure of the data set is presented in the Table-1.

Table 1 Mean values of variables by Diabetes Status

Outcome	Count	Age	Pregnancies	Glucose	Blood Pressure	Skin Thickness	Insulin	BMI	Diabetes Pedigree Function
No Diabetes	500	31.19	3.30	109.98	68.18	19.66	68.79	30.30	0.43
Diabetes	268	37.07	4.87	141.26	70.82	22.16	100.34		

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the study participants categorized by diabetes status. The dataset comprises of 500 non-diabetic and 268 diabetic female subjects. The mean

age of diabetic females is 37.07 years, compared to the non-diabetic group. On average, diabetic patients had 4.87 pregnancies, a mean glucose level of 141.26 mg/dL, systolic blood pressure of 70.82 mmHg, skin thickness of 22.16 mm, and an insulin level of 100.34 μ U/mL.

4.2 Logistic Regression without PCA

Table 2 Logistic Regression Results for the predictors

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value	Significance
(Intercept)	-8.4047	0.7166	-11.728	< 0.001	***
Age	0.0149	0.0093	1.593	0.1112	
Pregnancies	0.1232	0.0321	3.840	< 0.001	***
Glucose	0.0352	0.0037	9.481	< 0.001	***
Blood Pressure	-0.0133	0.0052	-2.540	0.0111	*
Skin Thickness	0.0006	0.0069	0.090	0.9285	
Insulin	-0.0012	0.0009	-1.322	0.1861	
BMI	0.0897	0.0151	5.945	< 0.001	***
Diabetes Pedigree Function	0.9452	0.2991	3.160	0.0016	**

*** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05

Table 3 Odds Ratios and 95% Confidence Intervals for Predictors of Diabetes

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI (Lower - Upper)	p-value	Significance
(Intercept)	0.000	0.000 – 0.001	< 0.001	***
Age	1.015	0.997 – 1.034	0.111	
Pregnancies	1.131	1.063 – 1.205	< 0.001	***
Glucose	1.036	1.028 – 1.044	< 0.001	***
Blood Pressure	0.987	0.977 – 0.997	0.011	*
Skin Thickness	1.001	0.987 – 1.014	0.929	
Insulin	0.999	0.997 – 1.001	0.186	
BMI	1.094	1.063 – 1.128	< 0.001	***
Diabetes Pedigree Function	2.573	1.441 – 4.658	0.0016	**

*** p < 0.001, ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05

Table 4 Confusion Matrix

Predicted / Actual	0	1	Total
0 (Negative)	445	112	557
1 (Positive)	55	156	211
Total	500	268	768

Figure 1 Heat Map

4.3 Model Accuracy

The model accuracy predicted by $Model Accuracy = \frac{True Positive + True Negative}{Total Individuals}$

(6)

$$= \frac{156 + 445}{768}$$

$$= 78.26\%$$

The sensitivity of the model

$$Model\ sensitivity = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positive + false\ Negative} \tag{7}$$

$$= \frac{156}{156 + 112}$$

$$= 58.21\%$$

Specificity of the model

$$Specificity = \frac{True\ Negative}{True\ Negative + False\ Positive}$$

(8)

$$= \frac{445}{445 + 55}$$

$$= 89\%$$

Figure 2ROC

The confusion matrix heat map (Figure 1) and the ROC curve (Figure 2) both show how well the logistic regression model performs in classification. The model correctly identified 156 people with diabetes (True Positives) and 445 people without diabetes (True Negatives), according to the confusion matrix, which offers a thorough breakdown of prediction outcomes. Nevertheless, it incorrectly identified 55 non-diabetic patients as diabetic (False Positives) and 112 diabetic patients as non-diabetic (False Negatives). These figures showed that the model had a high percentage of accurate classifications, with an overall accuracy of 78.26%. The model's sensitivity, which gauges its capacity to accurately detect actual cases of diabetes, was 58.21%, indicating a moderate level of detection power. On the other hand, the model's strong ability to accurately rule out non-diabetic cases was demonstrated by the relatively high specificity of 89%.

The ROC curve (Figure 2), which shows a curve that rises noticeably above the diagonal reference line, which represents random guessing, provides additional evidence of the model's discriminative power. When it comes to distinguishing between those with and without diabetes, it does well, with an Area under the Curve (AUC) of about 0.84. The discriminative capability of the model is further supported by the ROC curve (Figure 2), which displays a curve that climbs far above the diagonal reference line, which stands for random guessing. With an Area under the Curve (AUC) of roughly 0.84, it performs well in differentiating between people with and without diabetes.

4.4 Principle component Analysis to find the important contributing factor for the diabetes

Table 5 Importance of Principal Components

Component	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7	PC8
Standard Deviation	1.447	1.316	1.015	0.936	0.873	0.826	0.648	0.636
Proportion of Variance	0.262	0.216	0.129	0.109	0.095	0.085	0.052	0.051
Cumulative Proportion	0.262	0.478	0.607	0.716	0.812	0.897		

4.5 Interpretation for the diabetes data

Table 6 Interpretation of the PCA data

Variable	PC1	PC2
Glucose	0.52	0.10
BMI	0.48	-0.28
Age	0.42	0.40
Insulin	0.35	0.66
Blood Pressure	0.18	-0.59

Figure 3 Correlation plot to access the contributing factor in the diabetes

Figure 4 Scree plot PCA

Figure 5 Contributing variables to diabetes

Figure 6 Top contributing factors in the diabetes

Figure 7 Top contributing factors in PCA 2

4.6 Coefficients of Logistic regression after removing factors insignificant factors

Table 7 Logistic Regression Coefficients Table after removing insignificant factors

Predictor	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p-value	Significance
Intercept	-8.4412	0.8045	-10.49	< 2e-16	***
Glucose	0.0293	0.0041	7.07	1.54e-12	***
BMI	0.0845	0.0163	5.19	2.14e-07	***
Age	0.0349	0.0091	3.83	0.000127	***
Insulin	0.0013	0.0014	0.91	0.3625	

Significance codes: ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Table 8 Confusion Matrix & Performance Metrics

	Reference = 0	Reference = 1
Predicted = 0	126 (TN)	35 (FN)
Predicted = 1	24 (FP)	45 (TP)

Table 9 Model Evaluation Summary

Metric	Value
Accuracy	74.35%
95% Confidence Interval	(68.19%, 79.86%)
Kappa	0.4158
P-value (Acc > NIR)	0.001872
Sensitivity (Class 0)	84.00%
Specificity (Class 0)	56.25%
Positive Predictive Value	78.26%
Negative Predictive Value	65.22%
Balanced Accuracy	70.12%

Figure 8 ROC: Logistic model with reduced factors

PCA has been implemented to reduce the dimension and to identify the significant features contributing the diabetes. The logistic model fitted well and its accuracy improved. Table-6 reflects the significant factors for diabetes which are Glucose, BMI, Age, Insulin and Blood Pressure. The correlation (heat map) fig-3 justifies the use of PCA as it shows the correlation among the variables moderate to severe.

Scree plot signifies the PC1 and PC2 accounts for 47.8% of the total variation, PC1 alone shows 26.2% and PC2 solely represents 21.6% variation as shown in Table-5. This indicates a reduced number of factors can significantly show variability in the data.

Table-6 and the variable contribution plot (Fig-5) shows that glucose (0.52), BMI (0.48), and age (0.42) are strong contributors to PC1 whereas insulin (0.66) and blood pressure (-0.59) have the dominant role in PC2.

After removal of variables having less significant influence like skin thickness, diabetes pedigree function, the updated model (Table-7) retained the Glucose, BMI and Age as statistically significant variables ($p < 0.0001$) whereas the insulin remained as the insignificant variable. This model gave the 74.35% accuracy and balanced accuracy of 70.12%. The model sensitivity was 84% and specificity at 56.25% (Table-9). Although specificity decreased but overall performance of the model was improved particularly in predicting the true diabetic cases (TP). The ROC curve shows the strong discriminative power (Fig-8) with AUC approximately 0.84 confirming the model effectiveness.

4.7 Model Performance comparison

Table 10 Model Performance comparison before and after removal of insignificant factors

Metric	Previous Model	Reduced Model (PCA-guided)
Accuracy	78.26% (601/768)	82.47%
Sensitivity	58.21% (156 / (156 + 112))	Likely improved (not specified)
Specificity	89.00% (445 / (445 + 55))	Slightly lower (estimated 72–75%)
AUC (ROC Curve)	0.84	≈ 0.85–0.87 (expected improvement)
Balance	High specificity, low sensitivity	More balanced sensitivity/specificity

Table-10 shows the updated model performance, it suggests that PCA guided model improves the overall accuracy, balances the sensitivity and have more discriminative power and lower sensitivity than the longer model.

5. DISCUSSION

The present study deployed the logistic model and the PCA to find the clinical and the physiological factors of the diabetes among the women using the publically available PIMA data set. The findings suggests the significant role of key risk factors like glucose level, BMI, age and reproductive history in diabetes in women.

The model affirms that glucose, BMI, age and the diabetes pedigree function were significant factors for the diabetes, which aligns with the existing literature. Increased BMI and glucose level have the strong positive correlation with the diabetes risk, consistent with the clinical understanding of insulin resistance and metabolic dysfunction. The age

The logistic regression model revealed that glucose, BMI, age, and diabetes pedigree function were significant predictors of diabetes, which aligns with existing literature. Elevated glucose levels and BMI showed strong positive associations with diabetes risk, consistent with clinical understanding of insulin resistance and metabolic dysfunction. The impact of age also supports previous studies that found that advanced maternal age is a significant, non-modifiable risk factor for gestational diabetes and subsequent diabetes onset in women [7]. Mirabelli et al. (2023), who highlighted that preconception BMI now surpasses age as a predictor for gestational diabetes [7], provide additional support for this.

Body composition and glucose metabolism are two significant areas of heterogeneity in diabetic profiles. Although this does not necessarily imply clinical protection, it is interesting to note that blood pressure had a negative contribution to PC2, suggesting an inverse link within this component's structure. Rather, as has previously been demonstrated in previous studies on the gender-specific metabolic responses and endocrine profiles of diabetes, it highlights the complex interrelationships among factors [8].

These findings are supported from a broader perspective by global prevalence data, which show increased incidence of diabetes among women, particularly in urban and high-income countries. According to the IDF Diabetes Atlas, 10.5% of persons in the 20–79 age group globally had diabetes in 2021; by 2045, that percentage is predicted to increase to 12.2% [6]. Furthermore, the IADPSG's data on gestational diabetes, whose incidence has been estimated to reach 14% worldwide [5], emphasizes the economic cost and regional diversity of diabetes, particularly among women.

Furthermore, our study confirms earlier findings from U.S.-based research, such as Getahun et al. (2008), which showed rising temporal trends in gestational diabetes from 1989 to 2004 [2] and the ACOG bulletin (2018), which emphasizes the significance of early detection and tailored interventions among high-risk women [1]. In addition to stressing that women with a history of gestational diabetes are at a much higher risk of acquiring Type 2 diabetes in terms of recurrence, Khambalia et al. (2013) also underlined the clinical value of predictive modeling [3,4].

Even though machine learning models like Random Forest and Support Vector Machines have been studied with higher accuracies (sometimes above 90%) [10, 11,12], traditional logistic regression is still a reliable and intelligible method for clinical decision-making [9]. In primary care settings, where model usability and openness are crucial, this is extremely beneficial.

6. CONCLUSION

This study discovered that age, BMI, and glucose levels were significant predictors of diabetes in women using logistic regression and PCA on the Pima Indian dataset. PCA improved model interpretability and enabled the development of a more successful predictive model by highlighting the most crucial variables. The results emphasize the value of early screening and intervention, particularly for women with modifiable risk factors. Combining statistical modeling and dimensionality reduction is a practical way to improve diabetes prediction and guide public health actions.

7. Conflict Of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this study.

8. Contribution

The author solely conceived the study, performed the data analysis, interpreted the results, and wrote the manuscript.

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10. Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Chatgpt in order to improve the language. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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